

A DISCUSSION OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION, ITS CHALLENGES AND DIFFICULTIES WITH ITS IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract. *The article revealed translation is a common activity that takes many forms and involves many methods. Simultaneous translation or interpretation is not a new concept, but is only possible because of the electronic devices that allow it. It has been underlined that simultaneous interpretation gives politicians and participants of different meetings to understand each other and to communicate without losing time and observing the emotions alongside the speech. This article evaluates the requirements and conditions regarding simultaneous interpretation.*

Keywords: *simultaneous translation, interpretation, interpreter's cabin, text-based interpretation, target language.*

Globalization along with international trade, politics, diplomacy, and sports - has been soaring during the last century or so. We observe two trends in all developed and developing countries around the world: interest in learning foreign languages - primarily English - and interest in translation. As José Ortega Y. Gasset wrote, translation is what unites mankind. We must clarify today that this statement is true, but only if the translation is performed by professionals.

Translations that take place almost simultaneously with the speaker's speech are referred to as simultaneous interpretations. Interpreters may usually be no more than one or two sentences behind the speaker. Occasionally, simultaneous translation equipment requires interpreters to work in soundproof booths. Speakers speak into microphones, and the interpreter listens to them through headphones, translating their thoughts to the interpreter's console's microphone. In the hall, listeners select the appropriate audio channel on their receivers in order to hear the translation in a language they understand. There may be more than one interpreter translating into different languages.

However, even though the simultaneous translation was invented as early as 1926, professional simultaneous translation only began after the end of World War II. It was used during the Nuremberg Trials when the international multilingual community prosecuted Nazi war criminals.

Interpreters who perform simultaneous interpretation use specialized and expensive equipment, which allows the translator to perform translations almost simultaneously with the speaker, so the speaker doesn't have to pause for translations. Depending on the pair of languages, the interpreter's experience, skill level, and individual characteristics, there is a time lag between the simultaneous interpreter and the speaker. However, it is important to remember that each individual's psychophysiological profile is unique, that is each interpreter may implement simultaneous interpretation in a slightly different way.

Here is the special equipment that simultaneous interpretation requires; a station or a cabin, microphone and two pairs of headphones for interpreters, radio headphones according to the number of people in need of translation.

With the use of simultaneous interpretation, events are organized (meetings of commissions, conferences, seminars, presentations, etc.) with the participation of a significant number of people in large auditoriums (conference halls). Two (sometimes 3) translators sit in the cabins, which replace each other every 20- 30 minutes (by agreement). Each translator is also paid for every hour in the cabin. Interpreting at conferences and other similar events, simultaneous or subsequent, is also called conference interpretation (the terms conference interpreting and conference interpreter are used more often in English).

Translations of speeches or presentations (slideshows) can be reviewed (or translated fully) in advance with the original text provided in advance. During the translation, the translator makes the necessary adjustments if the speaker strays off the original text, for example, telling a story about what happened to him yesterday on the way to the conference. This type of simultaneous translation is called text-based simultaneous translation.

During reports, lectures, and presentations, the speaker can read the information on the slide or refer to this information: "As you see on the slide ...". In this case, the simultaneous interpreter essentially makes simultaneous translation from the sheet. With Simultaneous Text-Based Interpreting and Simultaneous Sight Translation, first, the perception is made by ear, and then the received information is compared with the perceived visually. If the information received by ear differs from the written text, then the translator translates, relying only on auditory perception. The same thing happens when the speaker speaks too quickly and the interpreter does not have time to comprehend the information. If the translator has translated the entire text in advance and the speaker does not make any changes, the translator reads the translation already made by him. In this case, his work essentially boils down to reading a previously translated text, and the stress during work is not so high. In the modern world, with large flows of information and frequent conferences, simultaneous interpreters usually look through the texts of speeches or slides of the presentation, if they are provided in advance, make notes on terminology, but do not translate the entire texts. Interpreters hope for speakers' good speech, reaction, skills, experience and usually do not like to write very much, or they simply don't have the time and/or energy to make translations in advance.

In contrast to consecutive interpretation, in simultaneous interpretation, the perception of speech and the generation of speech in the translation is almost not separated in time, the memory is less loaded, and the interpreter does not enter into active interpersonal relationships with the conference participants. Usually, records are not kept in simultaneous translations, but sometimes it can be done.

"With simultaneous translation, even the most experienced translator will always lag behind the speaker. Translating the end of the phrase just uttered, he already listens and remembers the beginning of the next one. If at the same time, a long list of names, titles, numbers are given in the speech, additional difficulties arise. And it is here that colleagues always come to the rescue. They usually write down all the numbers and names on a sheet of paper lying in front of the person who translated, and when he reaches the right place, he reads these notes without straining too much memory. The translation is not only completely accurate, but it is also consistent.

"The rate of speech can be a problem in simultaneous translation. The average speech rate in British and American English is 120–150 words per minute.

Optimum for a simultaneous interpreter is considered to be a speech rate of 100-120 words per minute, and a rate of 150-200 words per minute (as professional English-speaking speakers say) is considered fast, reduces the quality of the translation, and leads to omissions and errors even with experienced work synchronized interpreters. The tempo of prepared speech is faster, so it is easier to perceive and translate unprepared speech. Interesting and, as it seems, promising is the transitional type of interpretation, which is known as simultaneous consecutive interpreting. In 1999, EU translator M. Ferrari, during consecutive interpretation, while making translation notes, simultaneously recorded a segment of speech on a device. Then, in a pause, he quickly put on his ear-sets and translated, listening to a segment of speech for the second time and relying on his notes as well. Experiments with such simultaneous consecutive interpretation show that double listening increases the accuracy (adequacy) of translation.

For a long time, psychologists believed that the same mechanisms operate in the perception and production of speech. Therefore, a person still cannot listen and speak at the same time: the translator is silent when he listens, and does not listen when he speaks. However, in simultaneous translation, the translator has a split attention mechanism. An inexperienced translator alternately switches to the speech of the speaker, then to the search for a solution and the delivery of speech in the target language. The synchronization mechanism functions successfully only if the translator has speech skills that operate without the active participation of consciousness. "By means of telegraphic perception". The perception of a word is reduced to the awareness of only some syllables that represent its general sound contour. It is important to train to achieve such a "split" of attention, trying to listen and speak almost simultaneously. In this case, apparently, different parts of the brain are involved.

Simultaneous interpreters acquire the skill of simultaneously listening and speaking when, as a result of practice, according to A. Welford's observations, they learn to ignore the sound of their own voice. Some linguists conducted an experiment together with some psychologists and found out that a significant part of the original speech is perceived by the translator against the background of his own speaking. According to different researchers and depending on the pair of languages, the shift in simultaneous translation (English time lag, or phase shift, or ear-voice span) is 0.5-11 seconds, but on average 2- 4 seconds or 4-5 words at an average speech rate. An experienced interpreter tries to keep a pace that is convenient for him, regardless of what tempo the speaker chooses. In passing, we note that consecutive interpreters, according to experiments by M. Lederer, also tend to keep their own pace of speech. According to K. Dejan Le Feal's calculations, the speech rate of the synchronist in comparison with the rate of the orator's speech ranges from 71% to 87%.

Thus, research and experimental data show that translation is indeed largely simultaneous. Another important component of simultaneous interpretation is anticipation in interpreting. Probabilistic forecasting is the use of past experience to help estimate the likelihood of future events. The redundancy of language, which is 70-85%, helps probabilistic forecasting. Probabilistic forecasting is present in speech and is probably inherent in all types of speech activity.

Not all theorists and practitioners of translation agree that probabilistic forecasting exists: "the translator is not able to predict the idea of a specialist from a foreign branch unknown to him"; "Translation ethics prohibit expressing a thought before the speaker has said it". However, we are not talking about predicting someone else's thought, and even from a field of knowledge

unknown to the translator, but about the ability to predict the further content of a message due to the redundancy of speech, and the redundancy of speech also increases due to intonation. In Russian translation studies, the idea that “probabilistic forecasting constitutes the basic mechanism of simultaneous translation” is firmly entrenched.

There are several advantages to simultaneous interpretation. Unlike consecutive interpretation, the speaker's speech sounds without pauses. This makes communication more dynamic. Today, knowledge of a foreign language is not uncommon, and many participants prefer to listen to a lecture in a foreign language in the original. Such people, as a rule, get annoyed when, during a consecutive translation, the speaker stops, and everyone listens to the translation;

In comparison with the use of subsequent translation, the time of the event is approximately halved, and the translation can be carried out simultaneously into several languages. There are also some disadvantages of simultaneous interpretation. There is more information lost than with consecutive translation and the translation is less accurate. For organizers, simultaneous interpretation is much more expensive than consecutive: the fees of simultaneous interpreters are high, plus the payment for the rental of special equipment as well as the need to involve at least two interpreters who know the subject of the event will;

Higher stress in translation due to the need to adapt to different manners of speech, pace, and accent there. Interpreters have certain requirements that must be met in order for simultaneous interpretation to be effective.

These are some of them; fast thinking in both languages, fast speech, quick reaction with the ability to get out of a difficult situation, the ability to distribute attention (“split attention”); mental and physical endurance, stress resistance, a solid stock of stable constructions, clichés, and phrases in both working languages; rich vocabulary in both working languages; competent speech in both working languages; the ability to concentrate, the ability to “disconnect” from external interference; automation of linguistic and speech means of expression (the ability to quickly find equivalents); good listening skills (listening comprehension); breadth of outlook, encyclopedic knowledge;

Consequently, globalization requires fast and high-quality interpretations in order to run modern businesses, processes in various institutions, and the like. This helps explain the high demand for quality interpretation. In addition to other kinds of translation, interpretation requires additional tools to accomplish the task, which means there is a need to make investments and hire people skilled enough to use all these tools. The learning process for those using these will take some time, in addition to the time that must be spent on updating tools and programs.

Besides the requirements and requirements for interpretation to be carried out, the article also compares the advantages and disadvantages. Interpretations have several advantages, including the possibility of seeing the expressions of the speakers, while information is lost during translation, and stress is a disadvantage. In light of the above given fact, we can conclude that interpreters need to constantly practice and stay up to date on developments in the field.

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